

DESIGN FOR DURABILITY OF POLYMERIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The durability, in the form of creep performance, has been analysed for a large series of polymeric composites based on thermoplastic matrices with glass fibres. Individual creep curves are described by a mathematical expression containing terms with an exponential dependence on time. The experimental data are well described. The parameters of the expression are determined as functions of stress. The creep curves are recalculated. The difference between predicted and measured values is in the range 0.2 - 0.4 %, and increases with creep time. Finally, the data are analysed by the method of neural network. It gives comparable results to other methods of prediction.

INTRODUCTION

The durability of polymeric composites is of relevance to products and components, since successful performance over an increasing life time is of concern to modern society. The designers need data and rules for the prediction of performance and lifetime.

The particular form of durability in the present study, is creep at a range of temperatures and environments. The designers will in this case be interested in the general creep curve (strain versus time) of the material, and the life time for a given allowable strain of the material. The necessary information is normally obtained from several series of creep experiments, and the recorded data can then be analysed in several ways. Some modelling, based on mechanisms and/or FEM calculations, will sometimes be added in the design task for a given component.

The present study is concerned with procedures for design, and comprises a number of ways to analyse experimental creep curves; the data are normally available in the form of tables listing strain versus time for each experiment, as well as testing parameters (like stress, temperature, environment) and materials identification.

The simplest use of the data would be in form of a *database search* where specific questions can be answered, such as "what data is available at a certain stress and/or temperature", and "what is the strain at a certain time". In practical use, it will be rare for a designer to require data exactly matching the recorded experimental data, and some form of interpolation of the data is needed. Therefore, the next level would be an analysis of *individual creep curves*

by a mathematical, empirical, relationship, followed by establishing relations between the mathematical parameters and the external test conditions as well as materials characteristics. This method will then allow recalculation of creep curves for a given set of test and material parameters.

The most general method will be a global modelling of *all creep curves* in a continuous iterative process, based on the principle of a neural network, where the network optimizes the model by the principle of cross-validation.

The present study describes various methods of presenting the experimental results and arranging the information such that it is convenient for the design process.

MATERIALS

The study comprises several series of polymeric composites. These are based on matrices of thermoplastic polymers of polyphenylene sulphide (PPS) and polyether sulphone (PES) with short glass fibres. The PPS-composites contain 21 vol. % glassfibres, and the PES-composites have 15 vol. % glass fibres. The fibres are reasonably well aligned by the fabrication process of injection moulding. Specimens for creep testing are cut at various angles relative to the fibre direction, with most specimens oriented with the loading direction parallel to the fibre direction.

The creep conditions are temperature from 20 °C to 140 °C, environment of air and water (with pH from 7 to 12) and stresses up to 120 MPa. A total of 285 samples are tested with different combinations of specific parameters:

- fibre angles: 0, 15, 30, 45, 60, 90 °
- temperatures: 20, 60, 90, 120, 125, 140 °C
- environment: air, water with pH= 7, 9, 12
- stresses: 5 to 120 MPa

The most common combination (group 1), with 56 specimens, is PPS with 21 vol. % glass fibres, at fibre angle 0°, environment water, and temperature 90 °C. Fig. 1 shows the distribution of samples over the range of temperatures and stresses.

Figure 1: The total distribution of test samples relative to stress and temperature, with the most common combination PPS - 0 ° - water - 90 °C (group 1) marked with circles

Figure 2: Sketch of mechanical model for the combination of elastic, visco-elastic and linear creep, corresponding to the first three terms of Eqn (1)

INDIVIDUAL CREEP CURVES

The creep curve of strain versus time is often described by a mathematical expression of the form:

$$\epsilon(t) = \epsilon_{el} + \theta_1(1 - e^{-\theta_2 t}) + \theta_3 t + \theta_4(e^{\theta_5 t} - 1) \quad (1)$$

The strain at time t is composed of an initial strain ϵ_{el} which occurs upon application of the creep stress σ_c ; ϵ_{el} is normally taken to be a (fully) elastic strain equal to σ_c/E , where E is the modulus of the material. The second term of Eqn (1) represents the primary creep stage with a diminishing creep rate, and with a total magnitude of strain of θ_1 . The third term of Eqn (1) represents the secondary creep regime with a constant creep rate. The final term of Eqn (1) represents the third creep stage with an ever increasing creep rate, leading to failure.

The form of the creep expression in Eqn (1) is empirical, and can be regarded as a convenient mathematical expression for describing a characteristic S-shaped curve. It does however also relate to simple mechanical models of springs and dash-pot units as sketched in Fig. 2. This covers the first three terms of Eqn (1). The relations between the mathematical parameters θ_i and the stiffness of the springs and the friction coefficients of the dash-pots are given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{el} &= \sigma/E_1 \\ \theta_1 &= \sigma/E_2 \\ \theta_2 &= E_2/\eta_2 \\ \theta_3 &= \sigma/\eta_3 \end{aligned}$$

An advantage of using an expression like Eqn (1) is that the data for the creep curve can be represented in an compact form, and that parameters such as strain at a certain time and minimum creep rate, can easily be derived by mathematical manipulations.

The determination of parameters in the expression (1) was performed for each specimen, i.e. for each individual creep curve. Well known methods based on the Levenberg-Marquardt procedure [1], are used as implemented in packages like MINPACK [2] and ODRPACK [3]. The method uses the least squares principle for the deviation between functional values and experimental values. Few problems were encountered, the procedure requires a starting point for the iterative search, and suitable values could generally be found from the data by the use of simple algorithms.

The θ -parameters could generally be found with good accuracy, in particular values for ϵ_{el} , θ_1 , θ_2 and θ_3 . The parameters for the third creep stage, θ_4 and θ_5 , were in some cases difficult to establish, because the third stage "starts" late in the lifetime of the composite, while the mathematical form of the fourth term in Eqn (1) is "active" from time zero. The modelling of such experimental behavior requires a very small value of θ_4 combined with a rather large value of θ_5 . In several cases the third stage was non-existing, and in such cases parameters θ_4 and θ_5 were fixed to zero.

An example of the experimental data set and the analysis by Eqn (1) is shown in Fig. 3.

Creep parameters of interest to the designer could be the minimum creep rate and the time to reach it. From Eqn (1) and the condition $\dot{\epsilon} = 0$, the derived parameters are

$$t_{min} = \frac{\ln(\theta_1/\theta_4) + 2 \ln(\theta_2/\theta_5)}{\theta_2 + \theta_5}$$

Figure 3: Creep curve for PPS-glass composite with fibre orientation 0° environment water of pH = 11 at temperature 90 °C, the experimental points are marked by +, and the fitted curve by full line.

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{min} = \theta_1 \theta_2 e^{(-\theta_2 t_{min})} + \theta_4 \theta_5 e^{(\theta_5 t_{min})} + \theta_3$$

The values for the specimen in Fig. 3 are $\dot{\epsilon}_{min} = 0.00985\%/h$ and $t_{min} = 13.9 h$.

FAMILY OF CREEP CURVES AT CONSTANT TEMPERATURE AND VARYING STRESS

Eqn (1) is valid for a single experiment, i.e. for a given set of material parameters and test conditions. A first step to generalize the description is to make the θ -parameters functions of stress, at a given temperature. Since creep and in particular creep rate is often a power or an exponential function of stress, a simple proposal is to use

$$\theta_i = a_i \cdot \sigma^{b_i}$$

to describe the stress dependence. This type of dependence is used in some FEM-programs for creep, for example in ANSYS. This expression is conveniently plotted in double-log-diagrams:

$$\log \theta_i = a_i + b_i \cdot \log \sigma$$

Together with the obvious linear plot of creep stress versus ϵ_{el} , this analysis is presented in Fig. 4 which also shows the straight lines providing a least squares fit. The results is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{el} &= \sigma/87.2 \\ \log \theta_1 &= -1.72 + 0.592 \log \sigma \\ \log \theta_2 &= -7.27 + 4.41 \log \sigma \\ \log \theta_3 &= -8.89 + 4.36 \log \sigma \end{aligned}$$

Eqn (1) can then be written:

$$\epsilon(t) = \sigma/87.2 + 10^{-1.72} \cdot \sigma^{0.592} \cdot (1 - e^{10^{-7.27} \sigma^{4.41} t}) + 10^{-8.89} \cdot \sigma^{4.36} \cdot t \quad (2)$$

From this equation it is possible to re-calculate the creep curve of an individual experiment; this is demonstrated in Fig. 5. The calculated curve follows the experimental curve rather well, although with greater deviation than the individually fitted example in Fig 3.

A comparison of the calculated values from Eqn (2) and the values determined using the individual parameters for each curve is shown in Fig. 6. The x-axis on this curve is normalized, so that for each curve t_0 corresponds to the start time, and t_{max} to the end of life time

Figure 4: Parameters ϵ_{el} and θ_i for PPS-glass composites (group 1) plotted to obtain numerical values for Eqn (1); (a) σ vs ϵ_{el} ; (b) $\log \theta_1$ vs $\log \sigma$; (c) $\log \theta_2$ vs $\log \sigma$; (d) $\log \theta_3$ vs $\log \sigma$

of the individual samples; the y-axis is the deviation (error) between the strain calculated from Eqn (2) and Eqn (1). The curves, from top to bottom, are maximum error, average error plus one standard deviation of the error, average error, average minus one standard deviation of the error, and minimum error.

It is obvious that there are substantial deviations between the model and the data, and that the deviations increases with time. The data are useful as an indication of the precision with which one can hope to predict the creep strain using an expression of the form (2), or probably an expression of any other form, due to the intrinsic variation in creep samples and test conditions.

A common use of creep data is to record the time to failure, at a given temperature, as a function of creep stress; this information is shown in Fig 7, for the materials of group 1. Such data gives the designer an overall view of the lifetime under a given stress, but does not indicate any pre-failure damage of the material, and does not describe the strain-time history before failure. The analyses based on Eqns (1) and (2) are more informative, but of course more complex in terms of information required and time needed for analysis and design considerations.

Figure 5: Re-calculated creep curve for PPS-glass composite. experimental data marked by +, individually fitted curve marked by full line, re-calculated curve marked by dotted line

Figure 6: Comparison, for composites in group 1, of calculated creep strain versus time, presented as the difference between values found from Eqn (1) and Eqn (2), see text for explanation

Figure 7: Failure time versus log creep stress for PPS-glass composites of group 1

Figure 8: LUT network layout

Figure 9: LUT neuron

NEURAL NETWORKS

Finally, the data has been analysed using a Look Up Table (LUT) based, weightless neural network. The LUT network is a feed forward type neural network with an input layer, one layer of hidden neurons, and an output layer.

Fig. 8 shows the architecture of the LUT networks. They differ from "normal" backpropagation neural networks in several ways. The hidden neurons are LUT based discriminators,

whereas the more common McCulloch-Pitts neuron type compares the input vector to the weight vector connected to it. The LUT's are sparsely connected to the input layer, and the connections are "weightless" in the sense, that all existing weights have the value of 1. LUT networks can do everything that McCulloch-Pitts networks can do, and on top of this, they can learn and "unlearn" examples incrementally, and very fast. This makes it possible to perform a total "one-out" cross validation of the training set very fast, and that is the basis for using the system for higher order statistical analysis and optimal model building.

Fig. 9 shows the LUT neuron. The elements in the LUT's are integers. This is convenient for the training algorithm. The LUT neuron functions as follows: With an active input, the address decoder calculates the value of the binary input of the connections to the input pattern. The address decoder then selects the column in the LUT indexed by the value calculated. When the LUT is in recall mode, the output lines are zero (0) if the column selected has all zeroes, and one (1) otherwise. A more detailed description is given in [4, 5].

Data for *training of the network* was generated from Eqn (1), with the parameters determined for each sample, by calculating strains over the lifetime of each sample. A logarithmic distribution was selected, with 20 steps over the range $0.01 \cdot t_{max}$ to t_{max} , in order to get increased information on the primary creep stage. The network was trained simultaneously on the whole population of 285 samples, and a cross-validation was then performed on each datapoint. The results obtained are shown in Fig. 10. For comparison with the data in Fig. 6, data from samples in group 1 was selected, and the deviation (error) between the network predicted strain, and the actual calculated strain was determined for each time step, and the usual statistical parameters for the distribution determined. The result is shown in Fig. 11. The curves, from top to bottom, are maximum error, average error plus one standard deviation of the error, average error, average minus one standard deviation of the error, and minimum error. It is seen that the deviations are similar to those shown in Fig 6; the minimum and maximum curves are placed at larger numerical values, and have more scatter. The increasing deviations at long times are partly due to the way of selecting the 21 points with emphasis on the primary creep stage, such that datapoints for longer times are more sparse.

The creep curve for the PPS composite in Fig. 3 has been predicted by the neural network, and the 21 points are marked in Fig. 12. The recalculated creep curve from Fig. 5 is also included. The individual points from the neural network show similar deviations from the individual curve, these are both positive and negative. This indicates that the *shape* of the creep curve is badly predicted by the neural network.

The neural network provides a synthesis of all data points of a given population of creep curves, and takes into account simultaneously all parameters (materials characteristics, testing conditions, time) in the prediction of strain. The quality of these predictions is shown in Fig. 10 for a total of $285 \cdot 21 = 5985$ individual points.

CONCLUSION

A large number of creep curves has been analysed using different methods, and the results compared. Individual creep curves are well described by an expression of the form (1), and this equation provides a convenient means for representation of creep data.

Data from creep experiments at varying stress levels, but with other conditions constant, has been analysed with the purpose of determining parameters in an equation of the form of (2). The variation between the predicted values and the actual measured values is in the range 0.2-0.4 %, and the discrepancies increase with time.

Finally, the data has been analysed using a neural network. This provides a simple method for interpolation in the data, and performs on par with alternative methods if the required

Figure 10: The creep strains predicted through the neural network compared to “measured” strain from Eqn (1)

Figure 11: Comparison for composites in group 1 of creep strain predicted through the neural network and “measured strains” from Eqn (1), see text for explanation

Figure 12: Creep curve for PPS-glass composite of Fig. 3, compared to predictions of strains (21 points marked with \times) from the neural network; the recalculated curve is shown as dotted line

information is questions like: what is the expected strain at a given time for given conditions. It does not provide an analytical expression of the creep curve, and it does not predict the shape of the creep curve well.

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